

Technical Description, Modelling, and Simulation of the U-CAT Underwater Vehicle

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1 Hardware and Modelling

This section presents the foundational concepts necessary for understanding the dynamics and control of the underwater vehicle, U-CAT. It initiates with a description of the experimental platform, followed by discussions on body dynamics and fin dynamics modelling. Finally, control allocation is also presented, determining how control inputs are translated into vehicle actions.

1.1 Experimental platform U-CAT

Figure 1: a) View of U-CAT robot during an inspection mission in a submerged structure. b) Illustration of U-CAT's fins configuration. The robot's front right, rear right, rear left, and front left fins are denoted by FR, RR, RL, and FL, respectively. In equations, these fins are indexed as 1, 2, 3, and 4, corresponding to FR, RR, RL, and FL.

U-CAT, as shown in Figure 1a, is a bio-inspired AUV, conceived during the European Union's 7th Framework ARROWS project [1]. Unlike similar underwater robots, U-CAT's unique four-finned design is driven purely by the specific needs and environmental challenges of shipwreck exploration. Its primary function is to capture detailed video footage of underwater sites. To cater to the specific demands of archaeological shipwreck inspections [2], a design of a 4-flipper structure to manage its 6-DOFs was created. The orientation of the four motors powering the fins is depicted in Figure 1b, enabling the robot's omnidirectional movement. The fins are outward-facing to maximize forward thrust, while side-to-side control is reserved for meticulous movements in tight areas. Additionally, U-CAT's weight distribution ensures its natural stability, with its centre of mass positioned just below its buoyancy centre. Comprehensive technical details about U-CAT are in Table 1.

Table 1: Main technical specifications of the U-CAT robot

Technical specification	Specification / Description
Onboard camera	PointGrey Chameleon 2
Hydrophones	Aquarian Audio H1c
Motors	Maxon EC-max
Attitude sensor	MPU-6050 IMU
Depth sensor	GEMS 22CS Series Pressure Sensor
Batteries	4x HP Compaq NX8200 8cell batteries
Maximal speed (surge)	0.25 m/s
Maximal depth	100m
Autonomy	~6 hours
Mass	19 Kg
Dimensions	560mm × 329mm × 258mm
Fins' material	Zhermack Elite Double 22

1.2 Kinematics modelling

This section focuses on the modelling of underwater vehicles. The modelling objective is to find a mathematical representation that captures the real system's behaviour, which can later be used for simulation purposes or control law synthesis.

1.2.1 Coordinates system

Various representations exist for marine vehicles. This section introduces the most common representation, as defined in 1950 by the SNAME (Society of Naval Architects and Marine Engineers) and detailed in [3]. This representation necessitates the definition of two frames:

- **Fixed Frame:** This frame, attached to the Earth, has its origin O and the orientation of the axes x , y and z following the North East Down (NED) convention will be used, where O_x points north, O_y points east, and O_z is oriented downwards perpendicular to the Earth's surface. The origin O is positioned on the surface at a fixed point within the robot's operational zone. This frame will be denoted as R_n , with index 'n' denoting NED.
- **Mobile Frame:** This frame, attached to the vehicle, is denoted as R_b (with index 'b' indicating Body fixed frame). The centre O is located at the vehicle's centre of gravity. The axes O_x , O_y , and O_z are aligned with the vehicle's primary symmetry axes. The O_x axis (longitudinal) points towards the vehicle's front, the O_y axis (transversal) points to starboard, and the O_z axis (normal) points downwards.

The state vector representing the vehicle's position and orientation in the earth frame R_n is denoted as $\eta = [x, y, z, \phi, \theta, \psi]^T$. The coordinates (x, y, z) , measured in meters, represent the position of the frame R_b centre within the frame R_n . The angles ϕ , θ , and ψ , in radians, describe the orientation of the frame R_b relative to the frame R_n . These angles are respectively termed roll, pitch, and yaw.

The transformation from frame R_n to frame R_b can be expressed in matrix form. The associated rotation matrix is R_n^b . Conversely, to go from frame R_b to frame R_n , the rotation matrix R_b^n is used. These matrices are related by:

$$R_n^b = (R_b^n)^{-1} = (R_b^n)^T \quad (1)$$

The vector $\mathbf{v} = [u, v, w, p, q, r]^T$ aggregates linear and angular velocities in the frame R_b associated with the vehicle.

The velocities u , v , and w , in m/s , correspond to the velocities along the vehicle's axes O_x , O_y , and O_z . They are respectively termed surge (longitudinal speed), sway (transversal speed), and heave. The rotational p , q , and r , in rad/s , are the roll, pitch, and yaw velocities of the vehicle.

Figure 2: Illustration of the Earth Fixed Frame R_n (North East Down convention) and the robot's Body Fixed Frame R_b . ([Publication I] ©2020 Wiley Periodicals LLC)

1.2.2 Kinematic Model:

Euler representation

The derivative $\dot{\eta}$ of the state vector η in frame R_n can be computed from the velocities v in frame R_b using the relation:

$$\dot{\eta} = J(\eta)v \quad (2)$$

Where $J(\eta)$ is a transformation matrix defined as:

$$\dot{\eta} = \begin{bmatrix} R_b^n & O_{3 \times 3} \\ O_{3 \times 3} & \Theta \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

R_b^n is the previously described rotation matrix, used to calculate the linear velocities $\dot{x}, \dot{y}, \dot{z}$ in the frame R_n based on the linear velocities u, v, w in the mobile frame R_b .

Θ is the transformation matrix used to compute the derivatives $\dot{\phi}, \dot{\theta}, \dot{\psi}$ of the nautical angles from the angular rotation velocities p, q, r .

These matrices depend on the vehicle's orientation and are expressed as:

$$R_b^n = \begin{bmatrix} c\psi c\theta & -s\psi c\theta + c\psi s\theta s\phi & s\psi s\theta + c\psi s\theta c\phi \\ s\psi c\theta & c\psi c\theta + s\psi s\theta s\phi & -c\psi s\theta + s\psi s\theta c\phi \\ -s\theta & c\theta s\phi & c\theta c\phi \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

and

$$\Theta = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & s\phi t\theta & c\phi t\theta \\ 0 & c\phi & -s\phi \\ 0 & \frac{s\phi}{c\theta} & \frac{c\phi}{c\theta} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

Where ϕ, θ , and ψ are the previously defined nautical angles, and $c. = \cos(.), s. = \sin(.),$ and $t. = \tan(.).$

Quaternion representation

Quaternions are an efficient orientation representation for movements in 6-DOF [4]. More specifically, unit quaternions $q \in \mathbb{S}^3$, having the property $\|q\| = 1$ are used. They can be represented as a vector $q = (\mu, \varepsilon)$ constituting the quaternion's scalar $\mu \in \mathbb{R}$ and vector $\varepsilon \in \mathbb{R}^3$ parts. We define the inverse of a unit quaternion as its complex conjugate:

$$q^{-1} = \bar{q} = \begin{bmatrix} \mu \\ -\varepsilon \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{S}^3 \quad (6)$$

and the unit quaternion's identity as:

$$1_q = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0_{3 \times 1} \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{S}^3 \quad (7)$$

Furthermore, we can define quaternion multiplication as:

$$q_1 \odot q_2 = \begin{bmatrix} \mu_1 \mu_2 - \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_1^T \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_2 \\ \mu_1 \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_2 + [\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_1]_{\times} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

where $[\cdot]_{\times} \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$, denotes the skew-symmetric matrix representation

The position of an underwater vehicle in the three-dimensional space can be uniquely defined by a vector $p \in \mathbb{R}^3$ describing the origin of the body fixed frame with respect to a fixed inertial frame. The attitude of an underwater vehicle in three-dimensional space can be represented by a rotation matrix $R \in SO(3)$ mapping the axes of the body fixed frame onto those of the inertial frame. The vehicle's kinematics can then be written using the linear $v \in \mathbb{R}^3$ and angular $w \in \mathbb{R}^3$ velocities expressed in body fixed frame, in the following form:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{p} &= Rv \\ \dot{R} &= R[w]_{\times} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

For efficient and intuitive representation the rotation matrix can be represented by various three-parameter parametrizations such as Tate-Brian or Euler angles [5]. However, none of those parametrizations is globally non-singular, which makes them less conducive for use of 6-DOF vehicle control. An alternative solution is the use of the unit quaternion [6]. The map from a unit quaternion to a rotation matrix $R(q) : \mathbb{S}^3 \rightarrow SO(3)$ is described by:

$$R(q) := I_3 + 2\mu[\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}]_{\times} + 2[\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}]_{\times}^2 \quad (10)$$

Based on the definition in (8) R is a group homomorphism satisfying:

$$R(q_1)R(q_2) = R(q_1 \odot q_2) \quad (11)$$

and additionally $R^{-1}(q) = R^T(q) = R(q^{-1})$, as well as $R(1_q) = R(-1_q) = I_3$

Subsequently, the kinematic equations can be rewritten as:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{p} &= R(q)v \\ \dot{q} &= \frac{1}{2}q \odot \chi(w) = T(q)w \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

with $\chi : \mathbb{R}^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^4$ defined as:

$$\chi(w) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ w \end{bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

and $T(q)$ as:

$$T(q) = \frac{1}{2} \begin{bmatrix} -\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^T \\ \mu I_3 + [\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}]_{\times} \end{bmatrix} \quad (14)$$

1.3 Dynamics Modelling

In general, the NED frame is considered a Galilean frame even though it's fixed to the Earth's surface. This is because the forces on the vehicle due to Earth's rotation are negligible compared to hydrodynamic forces [7]. Below are the different forces acting on the vehicle:

1.3.1 Inertial matrix:

The vehicle's inertia matrix $M \in \mathbb{R}^{6 \times 6}$ is given by:

$$M = \begin{bmatrix} m & 0 & 0 & 0 & mz_g & -my_g \\ 0 & m & 0 & -mz_g & 0 & mx_g \\ 0 & 0 & m & my_g & -mx_g & 0 \\ 0 & -mz_g & my_g & I_x & -I_{xy} & -I_{xz} \\ mz_g & 0 & -mx_g & -I_{yx} & I_y & -I_{yz} \\ -my_g & mx_g & 0 & -I_{zx} & -I_{zy} & I_z \end{bmatrix} + M_{am} \quad (15)$$

where m is the mass of the robot, $[x_g, y_g, z_g]$ denote the coordinates of the centre of gravity in R_b , and the matrix M_{am} is a matrix summarizing parameters describing the hydrodynamic effect of added mass [3] such that:

$$M_{am} = \text{diag} \{ X_{\dot{u}}, Y_{\dot{v}}, Z_{\dot{w}}, K_{\dot{p}}, M_{\dot{q}}, N_{\dot{r}} \}$$

1.3.2 Weight and Buoyancy:

Gravitational force (weight) and hydrostatic force (buoyancy) play crucial roles in an underwater vehicle's stability. Vehicles are typically balanced such that weight is nearly equivalent or marginally less than buoyancy for energy-efficient submersion and spontaneous surfacing during malfunctions.

Let B represent the magnitude of the buoyancy force (in N) on the vehicle, and W be the magnitude of the vehicle's weight (in N). If the vehicle's centre of gravity is positioned at (x_g, y_g, z_g) and the centre of volume at (x_b, y_b, z_b) in the frame R_b tied to the vehicle, the hydrostatic forces and moments vector, f_G , is expressed in R_b as:

$$f_G = G(\eta) = \begin{bmatrix} -(W - B)s\theta \\ (W - B)c\theta s\phi \\ (W - B)c\theta c\phi \\ (y_g W - y_b B)c\theta c\phi - (z_g W - z_b B)c\theta s\phi \\ -(x_g W - x_b B)c\theta c\phi - (z_g W - z_b B)s\theta \\ (x_g W - x_b B)c\theta s\phi + (y_g W - y_b B)s\theta \end{bmatrix} \quad (16)$$

1.3.3 Hydrodynamic Damping:

The combined damping forces, f_D , are represented as [3]:

$$f_D = -D(v)v = -(D_l + D_n(v))v \quad (17)$$

Where $D_l \in \mathbb{R}^{6 \times 6}$ is the linear damping matrix, $D_n(v) \in \mathbb{R}^{6 \times 6}$ is the non-linear damping matrix, and $v = [u, v, w, p, q, r]^T$ is the vector of translational and rotational velocities in the vehicle's frame.

Often, $D(v)$ is approximated as diagonal such as:

$$D_l = \text{diag} \{D_u, D_v, D_w, D_p, D_q, D_r\} \quad (18)$$

$$D_n(v) = \text{diag} \{D_{nu}|u|, D_{nv}|v|, D_{nw}|w|, D_{np}|p|, D_{nq}|q|, D_{nr}|r|\} \quad (19)$$

1.3.4 Coriolis and Centrifugal Inertia Forces:

In the context of fundamental dynamics, the consideration of inertia forces is crucial. The combined effect of these forces, denoted as f_C , is represented through the matrix product:

$$f_C = -C(v)v = -(C_{RB}(v) + C_A(v))v \quad (20)$$

here, the matrix C_{RB} encompasses parameters typically derived from strip theory [8] or hydrodynamic simulations. The matrix C_A encapsulates parameters that describe the hydrodynamic impact of added mass, as detailed in [3]. the matrix $C_{RB}(v)$ is be defined as:

$$C(v) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & -mS(v_1) \\ -mS(v_1) & -S(I_b v_2) \end{bmatrix} \quad (21)$$

such that the matrix I_b describing the inertial moments is defined as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} I_x & -I_{xy} & -I_{xz} \\ -I_{yx} & I_y & -I_{yz} \\ -I_{zx} & -I_{zy} & I_z \end{bmatrix} \quad (22)$$

and the matrix $C_A(v)$ is be defined as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & S([X_{\dot{u}}u, Y_{\dot{v}}v, Z_{\dot{w}}w]^T) \\ S([X_{\dot{u}}u, Y_{\dot{v}}v, Z_{\dot{w}}w]^T) & S([K_{\dot{p}}p, M_{\dot{q}}q, N_{\dot{r}}r]^T) \end{bmatrix} \quad (23)$$

where $v_1 = [u, v, w]^T$, $v_2 = [p, q, r]^T$ and $S(\cdot)$ denotes the skew symmetric matrix of the following form:

$$S(\lambda) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -\lambda_3 & \lambda_2 \\ \lambda_3 & 0 & -\lambda_1 \\ -\lambda_2 & \lambda_1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (24)$$

1.3.5 Fins-Generated wrenches:

Thrust and torque produced by the U-CAT robot's fins depend on several factors, like the angle of attack, oscillation frequency, and amplitude. The resultant force is denoted τ :

$$\tau = [\tau_x, \tau_y, \tau_z, \tau_\Phi, \tau_\Theta, \tau_\Psi]^T \quad (25)$$

A more detailed derivation of τ based on fins actuation parameters is described in 1.4

1.3.6 External Disturbances:

Significant disturbances on the U-CAT robot, denoted as w , include marine currents and the umbilical when teleoperated. Though their modelling is challenging, there are many studies in this area. Chapter 4 in the reference [3] elaborates further.

After describing all forces acting on the vehicle, the vehicle's dynamic model is:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\eta} &= J(v)v \\ \dot{v} &= M^{-1}(-G(\eta) - C(v)v - D(v)v + \tau + w) \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

Where $\dot{v} = [\dot{u}, \dot{v}, \dot{w}, \dot{p}, \dot{q}, \dot{r}]^T$ is the vehicle's acceleration vector.

For the quaternion representation case, the 6-DOF kino-dynamic model, expressed in body frame, can also be formulated following Fossen's vectorial notation [9] as:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\eta} &= J(q)v \\ M\dot{v} + C(v)v + D(v)v + g(q) &= \tau + w \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

Where $\tau \in \mathbb{R}^6$ is the vector of wrenches acting as control input, while $\eta = [p, q]^T \in \mathbb{R}^7$, $v = [v, w]^T \in \mathbb{R}^6$ represent the vectors of the vehicle poses in the earth-fixed frame R_n and the velocities in the body-fixed frame R_b respectively. The Jacobian $J(q)$ combines the linear and angular kinematic mappings in the following way:

$$J(q) = \begin{bmatrix} R(q) & 0_{3 \times 3} \\ 0_{4 \times 3} & T(q) \end{bmatrix} \quad (28)$$

with its pseudo-inverse:

$$J(q)^\dagger = \begin{bmatrix} R(q)^T & 0_{3 \times 4} \\ 0_{3 \times 3} & 4T(q)^T \end{bmatrix} \quad (29)$$

1.4 Fin dynamics modelling

Figure 3: Visualization of forces on i^{th} fin based on the simple lift and drag model (model and figure adopted from [10]).

The dynamic model utilized to describe the fins of the U-CAT AUV is based on the rigid paddle model, as documented in [11]. This model's validity has been previously established and confirmed in research conducted by Georgiades et al. [10], where it was employed to simulate the underwater hexapod robot AQUA [12].

The fins of the U-CAT are assumed to generate horizontal (f_x) and vertical (f_z) forces relative to the fin's resting frame, as illustrated in Figure 3. The model relies on the following mathematical expressions:

$$\begin{aligned} f_x &= D_f \sin(\beta) + L_f \cos(\beta) \\ f_z &= -L_f \sin(\beta) + D_f \cos(\beta) \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

Here, β denotes the direction of the flow impinging on the fin, and D_f and L_f represent the lift and drag forces, respectively. These forces are defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} L_f &= 0.5\rho U_f^2 S_f C_{Lmax} \sin(2\alpha_{aoa}) \\ D_f &= 0.5\rho U_f^2 S_f C_{Dmax} (1 - \cos(2\alpha_{aoa})) \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

In these equations, α_{aoa} signifies the angle of attack, while U_f corresponds to the velocity of the flow impacting the fin. Additionally, S_f corresponds to the surface area of the fin. Lastly, C_{Lmax} and C_{Dmax} represent the maximum lift and drag coefficients of the paddle, respectively.

For a more comprehensive discussion on the modelling of fin forces, interested readers are encouraged to refer to Georgiades et al.'s work [10].

1.5 Control allocation

To produce the wrenches required to control the 6-DOF body motions, U-CAT's actuation follows an oscillatory movement described by:

$$\varphi_i^{osc}(t) = A_i^{osc} \sin(\omega_i^{osc} t + \varphi_{off_i}^{osc}) + \phi_{0,i} \quad (32)$$

with the oscillation amplitude A^{osc} , the oscillation rate ω^{osc} , the phase offset φ_{off}^{osc} and the zero direction of the oscillation $\phi_{0,i}$.

This will result in wrenches in body frame that can be modelled as:

$$\tau(\varphi^{osc}) = \sum_{i=0}^n [Ad_{T_{i,b}}] R(\phi_{0,i}) \mathbf{f}_i^{th}(\varphi^{osc}) \quad (33)$$

with n being the total number of fins. $R(\phi_{0,i})$ is the two-dimensional rotation matrix for fin i which maps the thrust produced along $\phi_{0,i}$ to horizontal and vertical forces in the rest frame of the fin.

$$R(\phi_{0,i}) = \begin{bmatrix} c\phi_{0,i} & 0 & s\phi_{0,i} & & \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & & 0_{3 \times 3} \\ -s\phi_{0,i} & 0 & c\phi_{0,i} & & \\ & & & 0_{3 \times 3} & \\ & & & & 0_{3 \times 3} \end{bmatrix} \quad (34)$$

Furthermore, $[Ad_{T_{i,b}}]$ is the adjoint representation of the homogeneous transformation matrix $T_{f,b}$ that is used to map wrenches produced in the static fin frame to the robot's body frame:

$$[Ad_{T_{i,b}}] = \begin{bmatrix} R(\Phi_i^{fin}) & 0_{3 \times 3} \\ [p_i^{fin}]_{\times} R(\Phi_i^{fin}) & R(\Phi_i^{fin}) \end{bmatrix} \quad (35)$$

with $p_i^{fin} = [x_i^{fin}, y_i^{fin}, z_i^{fin}]$ being the fin coordinates relative to the centre of the vehicle and with $R(\Phi_i)$ being the rotation matrix mapping from fin to body frame based on the orientation vector of the fin rest frame $\Phi_i^{fin} = [\phi_i^{fin}, \theta_i^{fin}, \psi_i^{fin}]^T$:

$$R(\Phi) = \begin{bmatrix} c\psi c\theta & -s\psi c\theta + c\psi s\theta s\phi & s\psi s\theta + c\psi c\theta s\phi \\ s\psi c\theta & c\psi c\theta + s\psi s\theta s\phi & -c\psi s\theta + s\psi c\theta s\phi \\ -s\theta & c\theta s\phi & c\theta c\phi \end{bmatrix} \quad (36)$$

To simplify the modelling, the instantaneous thrust f^{th} produced by each fin can be averaged over one oscillation period T_{osc} [13]:

$$\overline{f^{th}} = \frac{1}{T_{osc}} \int_0^{T_{osc}} f^{th}(\varphi^{osc}, \tau^{int}) d\tau^{int} \quad (37)$$

with τ^{int} being the integration time variable. Now by using (35) and defining $\psi^{fin} = |\psi_1^{fin}|$, $x^{fin} = x_1^{fin}$ and $y^{fin} = y_1^{fin}$ we can define the resulting wrenches τ in the body frame as a system of six algebraic equations with the fins' zero directions $\phi_{0,1-4}$ and thrusts $\overline{f^{th}}_{1-4}$ as independent variables written in matrix form $\tau = BX$:

$$\tau = \begin{bmatrix} \tau_x \\ c\psi_f \\ \tau_y \\ s\psi_f \\ \tau_z \\ \tau_\phi \\ y_f \\ \tau_\Theta \\ x_f \\ \tau_\Psi \\ M_a \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 & -1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & -1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & -1 & -1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 1 & 1 & -1 \\ -1 & 1 & -1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} c\phi_{0,1} \overline{f^{th}}_1 \\ c\phi_{0,2} \overline{f^{th}}_2 \\ c\phi_{0,3} \overline{f^{th}}_3 \\ c\phi_{0,4} \overline{f^{th}}_4 \\ s\phi_{0,1} \overline{f^{th}}_1 \\ s\phi_{0,2} \overline{f^{th}}_2 \\ s\phi_{0,3} \overline{f^{th}}_3 \\ s\phi_{0,4} \overline{f^{th}}_4 \end{bmatrix} \quad (38)$$

with $M_a = x^{fin} c\psi^{fin} - y^{fin} s\psi^{fin}$.

1.6 CPG algorithm

The CPG is used to ensure smooth and continuous transitions, which significantly reduces the effect of the non-modelled fin lateral forces. The equations of the CPG used to control the fins are adopted from [14]:

$$\dot{\zeta}_i^{CPG} = \omega_i^{osc} \quad (39)$$

$$\ddot{A}_i^{CPG} = K_{amp} \left(\frac{K_{amp}}{4} (A_i^{osc} - A_i^{CPG}) - \dot{A}_i^{CPG} \right) \quad (40)$$

$$\ddot{\phi}_{0,i}^{CPG} = K_{zd} \left(\frac{K_{zd}}{4} (\phi_{0,i} - \phi_{0,i}^{CPG}) - \dot{\phi}_{0,i}^{CPG} \right) \quad (41)$$

$$\dot{\phi}_i^{CPG} = \phi_{0,i}^{CPG} + A_i^{CPG} \cos(\zeta_i^{CPG}) \quad (42)$$

where ϕ_i^{CPG} is the zero-direction angle extracted from the oscillator and ζ_i^{CPG} , A_i^{CPG} and $\phi_{0,i}^{CPG}$ are state variables that encode the phase, amplitude and the zero-direction offset of the oscillations, respectively. The parameters ω_i^{osc} , A_i^{osc} and $\phi_{0,i}$ are control parameters for the desired angular rate, amplitude and offset of the oscillations generated by the control allocation.

1.7 Numerical parameters

Inertial and Coriolis Matrices Parameters:

The numerical values for the parameters related to M and $C(v)$, as detailed in Sections 1.3.1 and 1.3.4 respectively, are presented below.

Centre of Buoyancy and Gravity:

$$[x_b, y_b, z_b]^T = \begin{cases} [0.0, 0.0, -0.05]^T, & \text{with passive roll and pitch stabilization,} \\ [0.0, 0.0, 0.0]^T, & \text{when buoyancy center coincides with gravity center.} \end{cases}$$

Centre of Gravity:

$$[x_g, y_g, z_g]^T = [0.0, 0.0, 0.0]^T$$

Inertial Values:

$$[I_x, I_y, I_z]^T = [0.1574, 0.4646, 0.5115]^T$$

The off-diagonal inertial values I_{xy} , I_{yx} , I_{xz} , I_{zx} , I_{yz} , I_{zy} are set to zero due to the robot's symmetry along all three body-frame axes.

Added Mass Matrix:

$$M_{am} = \text{diag}\{40, 21, 149, 0.1269, 1.2052, 2.3064\}$$

Hydrodynamic Damping Parameters:

As presented in Section 1.3.3, the hydrodynamic damping effects are described as follows:

Linear Damping Matrix:

$$D_l = \text{diag}\{18.542, 100.7, 10.61, 0, 0, 2.313\}$$

Quadratic Damping Matrix:

$$D_n(v) = \text{diag}\{21.98|u|, 260|v|, 161|w|, 3.4244|p|, 2.1014|q|, 0.7226|r|\}$$

Fin model parameters:

The parameters used for simulating forces related to fin actuation (Section 1.4) are described in Table 2.

Table 2: Parameters for simulating fin dynamics and force to amplitude conversion.

ρ (kg/m^3)	S_f (m^2)	ω^{osc} ($\frac{rad}{s}$)	r_c (m)	C_d	C_{Lmax}	C_{Dmax}
997	0.02	4π	0.1	0.24	1.65	3.2

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